

Women and the Struggle for Identity: A Study of Santosh Kumar Ghosh's *Kinu Goalar Goli*

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Abstract

This paper would focus on Santosh Kumar Ghosh's Bengali novel *Kinu Goalar Goli* as a text which describes the struggle for an individual identity through estrangement, suffering and rootlessness embedded in the movement of the various women characters in the novel, both physically and psychologically, both externally and internally. The novel tells the story of Neela who has to leave their old house in a so-called civilized neighbourhood and move to 'Kinu Goala's Lane', a congested, dirty and isolated lane in the then Calcutta, due to severe financial crisis in her family. How she tries to adjust herself with the new place with all her efforts constitutes a large portion of the novel, but gradually it becomes the story of two other women, Shanti and Shakuntala who also fight their internal rootlessness and struggle desperately to establish individual identities of their own. Their search for a home of their own is also symbolic in their journey towards finding themselves. I would, therefore, try to explore the various nuances of internal estrangement that the three women characters suffer and how they successfully find a home and a world of their own where they can resolve the identity crisis that they have undergone for a long time in their lives.

Keywords: *identity crisis, movement, rootlessness, search for a home, internal estrangement.*

The issue of identity formation has often been a major concern for theorists and scholars of literature, as the concept of identity itself is very much fluid and complex. Moreover, when it concerns itself with women, the process turns out to be more complicated, for women, in a patriarchal society, are always deemed as someone's daughter, sister, mother, wife and so on. It is mostly difficult to consider a woman as an individual entity without the patronizing of a male member of the society. Erik Erikson has considered 'identity' to be

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. . . a subjective sense as well as an observable quality of personal sameness and continuity, paired with some belief in the sameness and continuity of some shared world image.¹

'Identity crisis' is a term used by Erikson himself in the context of identity development in the life cycle of a person's life. In his book, *Identity: Youth and Crisis*, Erikson suggests that it is a period when one undergoes a kind of conflict with himself or herself and frantically searches for a selfhood.² In literature, the issue of identity crisis has often attracted writers to explore the various nuances of identity formation from a socio-cultural perspective in their works. *Kinu Goalar Goli* is one of them.

Kinu Goalar Goli by Santosh Kumar Ghosh is a 1950-Bengali novel which describes the degeneration of human values in a semi-urban part of the then Calcutta in the aftermath of World War II. The novel is about a not-so-known and not-so-loved fictional lane of Calcutta and the lives that revolve around that particular lane. It beautifully captures the shifts and turns in the lives of three women who one by one come to this lane, leaving their previous residences and are shown to be in a continuous search of an individual identity and also of a place where they can feel belongingness. The first of these three characters under study is the novel's protagonist, Neela, a college girl who has to shift to '*Kinu Goalar Goli*' with her ailing mother and workless father. Her elder brother, Debabrata and his wife Amita also stay with them, but the relationship between them and Neela is one of bitterness and aversion. After being bankrupt, Neela's father, Shibabrata Babu fails to bear the maintenance of a big house and their gradual displacement from one house to another ultimately brings them to '*Kinu Goalar Goli*', a displacement which can be called degradation as well.

Neela, from the very beginning, has disliked their small rented room in '*Kinu Goalar Goli*', and the lane itself, for its untidy and congested nature: 'Little space, less light and wind.' (*Swalpo porisor, Swalpotoro alohawa.*; my trans.)³ The description that opens the novel vivifies the lane's being isolated from the rest of Calcutta, but at the same time its being no different from other blind lanes: 'After all, there is not only one Kinu Goala's Lane in the city.' (*Kinu Goalar Goli shohore to ar akta noy.*; my trans.)⁴ The lane is described as a place which is suffering from a deep-seated feeling of isolation from the rest of the city—reflected in the words:

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‘This lane could be a partner in nothing that the city owns; light, wind, vehicles, market—nothing means nothing.’ (*‘Ei golita shohorer konokichhur ongshidar hotey pareni; na alo, na batas, na gari-ghora dokanposar—na bolte kichchhuna.’*; my trans.)⁵— and an identity crisis, expressed through the words: ‘The life of Kinu Goala’s Lane, ...is somehow uncomfortable with its own existence.’ (*‘Kinu Goalar Goli’r pran ...konokrome apon ostitwo niye bibroto.’*; my trans.)⁶ But whatever it is, the lane, after all, has life in it: ‘Even this lane has life, then.’ (*‘Egoliro tabe pran ache.’*; my trans.)⁷ Neela realises this gradually and tries to grasp the little but extremely precious freedom that the 6/F bylane offers to her:

Strange! Even this house has a roof ... which ends touching the horizons of the open sky! ... One can even listen to the ripples of one’s own secret mind. (*Ashchorjo, e barrio chat ache, ...khola akasher seemana chhnuye tar shesh! ... Nijer nivrito monero kallol shone jaay.*; my trans.)⁸

The lane, in this way, becomes the ‘objective correlative’ of Neela’s mental state which is torn between ‘Poplar Park’, the place where they lived earlier and ‘Kinu Goala’s Lane’ where she thinks she is destined to live. Although she is well aware of her fruitless and hopeless future, she never bows down to anybody. Her sense of dignity and witty nature come out sparkingly when she refuses to digest the insults from either her brother or his wife and also in her satirical yet humorous comments to Abinash Babu, Amita’s uncle. Indrajit, a budding poet, identifies her free spirit when he says: ‘The gentleman [Abinash Babu] is crouched in the fear to catch a cold, while, you, sitting by his side, are absolutely comfortable, proud, fearless.’ (*‘Bhadralok sheeter bhoye akebare jorosoro; ... Tar pashe apni—akebare swachchhondo, udhwoto, nihshonko.’*; my trans.)⁹

The second female character to come to be associated with the lane is Shanti, for whom the image of the place starts changing in Neela’s eyes. Neela grows an affectionate relationship with Shanti, whose initial words clearly reflect her search for an individual identity: ‘Who has remembered who this Shanti was? Now I am only Manibabu’s wife—to call it in a sophisticated manner—...Mrs Sanyal.’ (*‘Ke chhilo kabe Shanti, ke mone rekhechhe? Ami akhon shudhu Manibabur bou—biliti kayday Mrs Sanyal.’*; my trans.)¹⁰ In the very beginning, she voices the universal malady of womanhood very simply: ‘Does a woman really have a name of her

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own?' (*Meyemanusher abar naam.*'; my trans.)¹¹ and immediately becomes one with Neela's own pursuit for an individual identity. Shanti has never wanted anything more than a house of her own and a secured life for herself, but the disorderly nature of her husband could only provide her with an unstable present and an uncertain future. She is continuously neglected by her writer husband who has preferred the world of his fictions over his real wife and this is what is most painful to her. Her husband, Manindra's sheer negligence towards her has robbed her of her individual existence. She ultimately finds herself to be nothing but a housekeeper who receives no love from Manindra, as if she has only been assigned with the duty to reassemble and rearrange things after they are left scattered by Manindra. But she is not one who would sacrifice herself so easily and accept a faceless existence. Instead, she indulges in a relationship with Indrajit, a young poet, in order to prove her worth to her husband and starts playing with Manindra, using Indrajit as a pawn, only to assert her existence, to exercise her will and to prevent Manindra from forcing her into oblivion. Shanti who would be considered a woman with no integrity of character, no sense of morality, ethics and conscience in the traditional eyes, when seen from a different perspective, would come out as a woman for whom her individual identity is the most important thing. After her marriage, she has already lost her individuality, as she herself realises in saying that her individual entity 'has already been effaced long ago.' (*...kabe dhuyemuchhe gyachhe.*'; my trans.)¹² Hers is an attempt to get it back from the hands of the patriarchal society which uses women to fulfil their biological, social, domestic and sexual needs and requirements, and finally forces them into oblivion, into a meaningless existence, if it can be called an 'existence' at all. Shanti has rebelled not only against her selfish husband engrossed in his own fictional world, but also against an age old system which marginalises women, robs them of their identity, and considers them only as a tool to serve its own purposes. So, in case of Shanti, the desperate attempt at retaining her individuality in the face of severe identity crisis due to her husband's neglecting attitude towards her ultimately leads her to a world of corrupting forces and degraded values. She loses to her husband again and again, but does not give up. Even when she is finally caught red-handed by her husband, to be in illicit relations with numerous producers of films, in order to make a career in films, only to cope with her husband, she makes Manindra confess, 'My faults are no less, Shanti.' (*Dosh to amaro*

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kom noy, Shanti.’; my trans.)¹³

Another life that gets involved with the existence of Kinu Goala’s Lane is Shakuntala’s. In the earlier phase of her life, not unlike Shanti and Neela, she has also run after the recognition and patronising of the males, represented through her husband. But she gradually realises that her husband, Banamali has been carrying the germs of a fatal disease in his body, as a result of numerous illicit relations in his youth. Shakuntala has tried her best to play the role that a patriarchal society would expect a woman to perform in such a situation, but a woman of her temperament fails to accept the injustice she has been subjected to. She decides to leave her husband’s house and start her life anew. After a lot of struggle with herself, she chooses an independent life with a nurse’s job in a hospital. Later being too exhausted to bear with the patronising surveillance of Mr Upadhyay, the in-charge of the hospital, she quits the job. In order to do something on her own, to live an independent and self-reliant life, she starts a nursing centre with three other girls, Anima, Geeta and Stella. In this way, after a long struggle for existence, she expects a life on which she will have the complete control. But it has never been acceptable to patriarchy to allow a woman exercise her independence, assert her individual identity, without waiting for the approval of any of the male members of the society. For Banamali, too, it seems difficult to accept his wife’s disregard towards his power. As a result, he does not leave her alone, and taking advantage of his job of a journalist, starts spreading such rumours about the nursing centre run by Shakuntala that it secretly runs a business of prostitution and does jobs like illegal abortions.

Shakuntala’s companions, Stella, Geeta and Lalita— who have been the source of her strength to fight against all odds and with whom her own individual existence has come to be associated automatically,— gradually leave the ‘Sevasatra’, the nursing centre, in the face of crisis. But Shakuntala does not blame them as each of them is in search of an individual identity. That is why Lalita chooses to marry the person she loves, while Geeta leaves secretly in search of a home for herself, and on the other hand, Stella feels safer to go back to her childhood love, Vivian with whom she hopes to find happiness and stability. Each of them is in desperate search to find a ‘home’, a search which becomes ironically symbolic as ‘home’ itself is a fluid concept.

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Banamali has been convinced that his plans of defaming the nursing centre or using Shakuntala's very own Geeta against her, will break Shakuntala's willpower into pieces and she will fall at his feet for sympathy and acceptance. But Shakuntala, even in the face of severe crisis, turns around and fights back till the end, remaining fixed and unchangeable in her decision about her own life: 'Go away, Banamali Babu! My decision is always irrevocable.' (*Apni bari jaan, Banamali Babu! Mawt amar badlayna.*'; my trans.)¹⁴ She never loses her conviction against the threats of Banamali who becomes the representative of the patriarchal society in his inability to tolerate the independent attitude of his wife. But she is invincible like a tigress, as the girls rightly point out that: 'her face after waking up looks exactly like that of a tigress.' (*...tar ghum bhanga mukhkhana thik baghinir moto dyakhay...*'; my trans.)¹⁵

The three central women characters of the novel, in this way, continue their futile struggle to find their identities through getting the approval and drawing the attention of the men in their lives, in the initial phases of their lives. But ultimately, they come to realise that identity itself is porous and fleeting. Notwithstanding that, they will at least not let the men be the guardians of their existence. Neela, for example, has run after a bit of recognition in the eyes of the men she has come across in different phases of her life. Initially it suggests a degradation in the standard of Neela's family to have moved to such a place like 'Kinu Goalar Goli', outside the gentlemanly circle of Calcutta's sophisticated people, at a time

. . . when this family was falling down during the days of its acute crisis—from Poplar Park to Bhabanipur, from Bhabanipur to Boubazar, from there to Kinu Goala's Goli... (*E poribar jakhon chorom durdoiber dine goriye pichhle porchhe—Poplar Park theke Bhabanipur, Bhabanipur theke Boubazar, sekhan theke Kinu Goalar Goli...*; my trans.)¹⁶

At the same time, Neela is also tossing around from Soumya and Manan of Poplar Park to Amita's uncle, Abinash Babu, and from Abinash Babu to Indrajit, a young poet, visiting her neighbourhood, with a false belief in finding her identity at their approval. She takes quite a lot of time to realise that 'the group of Manan-Soumya-Manish has disappeared for ever.' (*...temni miliye gyachhe Manan-Soumyo-Manisher dol.*'; my trans.)¹⁷ Neela, again, makes a mistake in believing that her identity will be asserted in the establishment of her superiority to Shanti, and so, she tries to

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win Indrajit over who becomes a tool to be used by both Shanti and Neela. In her cold war with Shanti, Neela forces her mind to do things she dislikes to attract Indrajit and to draw his attention. But when she is dreaming of starting a new life with Indrajit, she suddenly realizes that it is not what she has wanted for herself. In coming to this self-realisation, she is greatly influenced by Shakuntala's unbending attitude before the corrupting forces of the society and the bold assertion of her own will, in the face of patriarchal oppression and opposition.

Neela's final realisation is the result of her varied experiences in the initial phases of her life. In their previous residence at Poplar Park, too, Neela has tried in vain to woo Soumya, and Manan, both of whom have forgotten her with the change of their location to the disadvantaged, underprivileged '*Kinu Goalar Goli*', as if with this displacement, Neela's 'standard' has also fallen down. Her life takes a new turn when her brother, Debabrata and his wife, Amita leave Kinu Goalar Gali and move to Amita's rich uncle Abinash's house. Due to lack of money, both her college and training of music come to an abrupt end. It is similar to the movement of many of the residents of the house in the lane. It is as if similarly painful for the lane to let them go, for the lane has life, too: 'Even this lane has life, then.'¹⁸ Neela perhaps starts realising the pain of the lane which is no longer a lifeless entity for her, but one teeming with all kinds of emotions and sensations. It also keeps on searching for an identity of its own and undergoes an evolution just like the other characters of the novel. It, therefore, helps her to come to the drastic conclusion at the end.

'*Kinu Goalar Goli*', in this way, becomes a representative of the anxiety, alienation and rootlessness that all the three characters experience. Manindra also voices the same when he says: 'This lane has finished us, Shanti. If we have to live, we have to leave this place.' ('*Ei goli amader shesh kore diyechhe, Shanti. Bnachte hole e goli chharte habe.*'; my trans.)¹⁹ Each of the three women characters, Neela, Shanti and Shakuntala, has found in that particular lane a desperation for asserting its own existence. It seems to have lost its value in the eyes of the 'aristocratic' Calcutta which is sophisticated and advanced and which, therefore, neglects this lane and denies it any significance. Likewise, initially Neela runs after the attractive, orderless life of the budding poet Indrajit to get a bit of recognition and acknowledgement from him. It seems to her to be the

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most valuable thing to be achieved. But gradually she realises that she has never been a correct match for Indrajit. In her attempt at winning Indrajit's love, she is losing herself and her individuality. So, she ultimately decides to put an end to this game of winning a man's heart and attention, and follows the path her heart wished to take. 'Kinu Goala's Lane', therefore, becomes a fleeting yet significant phase in the lives of all these women characters, for, through the identity crisis of this non-living entity, they come to realise the meaning of their existence and to 'real'-ise their dream of an individual identity.

Endnotes :

- ¹ Quoted in Kanak Lata Tiwari, 'Identity Crisis—Indian English Fiction of Post 1980s', *International Journal of English and Literature*, 4.1 (2013): 6-10; p.6. doi:10.5897/IJEL12.067. Accessed 15 July 2019.
- ² Erik H. Erikson, *Identity: Youth and Crisis* (New York: W.W. Norton, 2000), pp.89-90.
- ³ Santosh Kumar Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli* (India: Mitra and Ghosh Publishers, 1950), p.2.
- ⁴ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.1.
- ⁵ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.2.
- ⁶ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, pp.1-2.
- ⁷ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.1.
- ⁸ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.10.
- ⁹ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.33.
- ¹⁰ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.7.
- ¹¹ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.7.
- ¹² Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.7.
- ¹³ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.98.
- ¹⁴ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.86.
- ¹⁵ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.57.
- ¹⁶ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.10.
- ¹⁷ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.99.
- ¹⁸ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.1.
- ¹⁹ Ghosh, *Kinu Goalar Goli*, p.109.